

Electrical and Optical Properties of Copper and Mercury Tartrate Crystal

BHUSHAN NIKAM¹, SACHIN NANDRE², HEMANGI PATIL³

¹ Department of Physics, Kai Sau. G.F.Patil .Jr.College, Shahada India.

² Dept.of Physics, NSS'S Uttamrao Patil art's and sci.college,Dahiwel Dhule,Maharashtra,India.

³ Department of Chemistry,. Kai Sau G.F.Patil Jr.College, Shahada India.

Abstract - In this study, the electrical and optical properties of Copper and Mercury Tartrate crystals were investigated. The crystals were synthesized using the gel method, and the band gap of both Copper and Mercury Tartrate was determined using UV-Vis spectroscopy. Single crystals were successfully grown via the gel method, and the composition-dependent optical and electrical properties were examined. All the crystals exhibited an orthorhombic structure. It was observed that with an increase in sodium (Na) content, the transparency of the crystals improved, while the band gap values decreased. The optical transparency of these crystals suggests their potential for nonlinear optical applications. Electrical conductivity studies revealed that the crystals exhibit semiconducting behaviour, with resistivity and conductivity following a variable-range hopping model. The optical properties, including band gap and absorbance, were also analyzed.

Keywords - UV- VIS, band gap, gel Method, Resistivity and electrical conductivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among various methods of crystal growth, gel diffusion technique is a relatively simple and inexpensive method used by many researchers [1][2][3]. Tartrate crystals have attracted the attention of many workers due to their interesting physical properties. Some crystals of this family are ferroelectric, some others are piezoelectric and few others are used in the control of laser emission[4]. Tartrates, as semi-organic materials, possess metal ions, bonded with the tartrate ions [5]. Technologically developed word is looking for nonlinear optical (NLO) materials for developing optical fibre communication system and optoelectronic devices[6]. Thus, semi-organic crystals, such as tartrates, which are grown to possess mechanical, electrical, thermal and optical properties suitable for a particular NLO application, are preferable. Tartrates, as semi-organic materials, possess metal ions, bonded with the tartrate ions[7]. The present study is focused on growing copper and mercury tartrate (semi-organic material) crystal and to study the samples electron transition, band gap, optical and electrical behaviour of material study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this experimental procedure, $C_4H_4O_6Cu$ and $HgC_4H_4O_6$ crystals were successfully grown using the single diffusion gel method. A sodium metasilicate solution with a density of 1.04 g/cm^3 was combined with $C_4H_4O_6$ at concentrations ranging from 0.5 M to 1.5 M. To maintain homogeneity and prevent localized ion accumulation—which could lead to uneven gelling and turbidity—a magnetic stirrer was employed for continuous stirring. The gel pH was carefully adjusted to a range of 4.0 to 4.5 using a digital pH meter, ensuring a controlled environment for crystal growth. To minimize evaporation and contamination, borosilicate glass test tubes were sealed with cotton plugs after the gel was poured. The gelation process was completed within 5 to 14 days, followed by an aging period of 72 hours for copper-based gels and 48 hours for mercury-based gels, enhancing stability. Once the gel was fully set, the supernatant solution was introduced carefully along the test tube walls to avoid disturbing the gel matrix. Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions gradually diffused into the gel, triggering the chemical reactions necessary for the crystallization of $C_4H_4O_6Cu$ and $HgC_4H_4O_6$. The detailed crystal formation process is described as follows:

The growth of CuT and HgT was achieved by controlled diffusion of copper and mercury ions through silica gel impregnated with tartaric acid [8]. To prevent evaporation and contamination, borosilicate glass test tubes were sealed with cotton plugs after the gel was poured into them. The gelation time varied depending on ambient temperature, and crystallization was initiated only after confirming proper gel setting. This approach ensured that the supernatant solution flowed smoothly along the inner walls of the test tube, preventing disturbances to the gel structure. The gradual diffusion of Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions from the supernatant solution facilitated the desired crystal formation process. After the designated maturation period, small dark blue-green crystals of copper tartrate and fine needle-like crystals of mercury tartrate—predominantly white and yellow with occasional red spots—began to emerge. The resulting crystals exhibited a plate-like morphology. The gel matrix appeared as a translucent, pale yellow-brown structure. However, when an excessive amount of HgCl_2 was introduced as the external reactant, both the supernatant solution and the gel body remained colourless, indicating an alteration in the reaction dynamics.[9]. Further enhancement in size, perfection, and colour was observed approximately 1 cm below the gel-solution interface. The complete crystallization process for mercury tartrate required approximately one month to achieve the desired crystal formation. The gel matrices were prepared by titrating sodium metasilicate solution ($\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with tartaric acid ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_6$). To achieve the required pH, a few drops of diluted acetic acid and potassium iodide were added. The prepared gel matrices were then set in straight borosilicate glass tubes to facilitate controlled crystal growth.

FIG.1 NUCLEI GROWTH POSITION OF COPPER TARTRATE.FIG.2 NUCLEI GROWTH POSITION OF MERCURY TARTRATE

Extensive investigations were conducted at intermediate pH levels ranging from 4.0 to 7.0, with increments of 0.1 M, as well as at varying gel densities between 1.02 g/cm^3 and 1.07 g/cm^3 . To optimize crystal growth, various tests were performed by adjusting the concentrations of the inner and supernatant reactants within a range of 0.1 M to 2.0 M. The interaction between the supernatant solution and the gel facilitated the formation of various crystal morphologies. The gel-grown copper tartrate and mercury tartrate crystals were characterized optically and electrically using a SHIMADZU UV-2450 spectrophotometer for optical analysis and a probe method for electrical conductivity measurements. The UV-Visible absorption spectra of copper tartrate were recorded at the Nano Research Laboratory, Department of Pharmacy, R.C. Patel College, Shirpur, covering a spectral range of 200–800 nm for copper tartrate and 200–400 nm for mercury tartrate. Measurements were conducted in single-scan mode at fast speed; with instrument settings including a 2.0 nm slit width, a light source change wavelength of 360.0 nm, and absorbance as the selected measurement mode. For the determination of electrical properties, conductivity measurements were performed using the probe method. A metering voltage was applied between two electrodes submerged in the sample, and the voltage drop—resulting from the resistance of the solution—was used to calculate conductivity per centimetre, providing insights into the electrical proofing properties of the grown crystals.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Optical Properties

Optical studies reveal that the crystal are transparent to visible and near Infrared (IR) wavelengths [10]. Measuring the band gap of material is vital in the semiconductor and nano-material solar industries. The band gap energy of tartrate crystal is calculated to determine its suitability for second harmonic generation at specific wavelengths. This calculation is performed using a straightforward conversion equation.

$$\text{Energy of the Band gap (eV)} = \frac{1240}{\text{wavelength of light in (nm)}}$$

TABLE-1 BAND GAP ENERGY OF COPPER AND MERCURY TARTRATE CRYSTAL.

Crystal	λ (nm)	Band gap Energy (eV)	Absorbance (AU)
CuC ₄ H ₄ O ₆	222.00	5.59	0.2489
HgC ₄ H ₄ O ₆	211.40	5.87	0.2177

The absorption coefficient is high at a lower wavelength and has a comprehensive transparency from 200 nm suggesting their suitability for second and third-harmonic generation of the 1064nm radiation[11]. It is a quantitative method and is called as UV-Vis is used to quantify how much light a chemical compound absorbs by measuring the amount of light that travels through a sample. Light passing through a reference sample has an intensity of 0.2489 AU for CuC₄H₄O₆ and 0.2177 AU for HgC₄H₄O₆; hence it satisfies and validates the optical characteristics. From the spectrum, it has been inferred that mercury tartrate crystals have a good transmission in the entire visible and I.R. region. The absorption coefficient is high at a lower wavelength.

B. Electrical Properties

The most important properties of metals are conductivity, resistivity, and dielectric strength. The electrical conductivity of the mercury tartrate crystals in this study is measured at temperatures in the range of 230 to 335 °K. The conductivity profiles of these crystals show a linear relationship with temperature. The V-I characteristics of the crystals are shown in below graph. Most conductivity measurements are made in an aqueous solution, and the ions responsible for the conductivity come from electrolytes dissolved in the water that the resistance value of gel-grown mercury tartrate is in mega ohm. It can also be observed that, as voltage increases, current also increases. As temperature decreases, resistance slightly decreases, and conductivity increases. According to the conductivity means, it is confirmed that mercury tartrate has a good conductor. which reinforces the above conclusion. Graph shows the $\log(k)$ against $\frac{1}{T} \times 10^{-4}$.

Figure 3: Electrical conductivity of mercury and copper tartrate crystal S/m.

The graphical representation shows that as the value of ratio $\frac{1}{T} \times 10^{-4}$ increases, log k linearly increases, then suddenly goes steadily. If the conductance of mercury tartrate in a solid solution of the prepared sample is dissolved in double distilled water and increased the volume of the solution is by 5 ml, conductivity decreases, and resistivity increases. Electrical conductivity measures a material's ability to conduct an electric current. Similarly after experiment for copper tartrate confirmed that it has a good conductor. The graphical representation shows that as the value of ratio $\frac{1}{T} \times 10^{-4}$ increases, the log k initially increases, then remains steady for some time, and then increases again. If conductance of copper tartrate solid solution of prepared sample dissolved in double distilled water with increased volume of solution by 5 ml. Conductivity decreases, and resistivity increases. Solid material exhibits varying electrical conductivities extending of magnitude ranging from 10^{-20} to $10^7 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$. This leads to the conclusion that the solid aqueous solution of copper tartrate confirms this range and shows conductivity and metal properties such as resistivity.

IV. CONCLUSION

The gel-grown copper tartrate crystals exhibit wide band gap energy, with measured values of 5.87 eV for mercury tartrate and 5.59 eV for copper tartrate. Ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy was employed to analyze the band gap energy and absorption characteristics of copper and mercury tartrate, confirming their optical properties. Furthermore, the electrical properties of the crystals were verified using a conductivity meter, demonstrating their conductive behavior. Among the various samples, crystals grown at a pH of 4.4 exhibited superior size and transparency, making them the most optimal for further applications.

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